

DEVELOPMENT OF A SORPTION-SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD FOR DETECTING COBALT (II) ION IN ENVIRONMENTAL OBJECTS USING IMMOBILIZED NITROZO R SALT REAGENT

¹Davronova N.F., ²Smanova Z.A.

¹Teacher-intern, Department of Chemistry, Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology

²Head of the Department of Analytical Chemistry, National University of Uzbekistan, PhD,
Professor

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Abstract. *The article proposes a sorption spectrophotometric method using an immobilized salt of nitroso R to determine the content of Co(II) ions in wastewater and soils around Akhangaron cement plant. The results of the proposed method were compared with the mass spectrometric (ISP-MS) method. Optimal conditions for the immobilization of nitroso R salt in a sorbent made of polymer fiber modified with polyacrylonitrile (PAN) polyethylene polyamine (PEPA) have been studied.*

Keywords: *immobilization, nitroso R salt, polymer sorbent, soil, wastewater, sorption, spectrophotometry, heavy metals, polyacrylonitrile, polyethylene.*

Introduction.

At present, the importance of iron, cobalt, nickel, and other trace elements for the vital activity of organisms has been proven, and small amounts are necessary for the normal functioning of biochemical processes. However, excess amounts of these metal ions can manifest themselves as potent toxins [1-3]. Cobalt and its compounds are widespread and are part of many anthropogenic activities. However, cobalt plays a biologically significant role as a metal component of vitamin B12. Excessive amounts of cobalt ions in the body, however, have been proven to lead to various undesirable consequences [4]. In the human body, when metal-metal prostheses corrode and undergo corrosion, soluble ions and corrosion particles spread into the environment [5]. Soluble metal ions released from cobalt-chromium-molybdenum (Co-Cr-Mo) prostheses have been found to exhibit cytotoxic effects on osteocytes. Furthermore, fluorescent imaging has shown a significant decrease in the number of live cells and an increase in the number of dead osteocytes treated with high concentrations of Co and Ni ions.

Research conducted by scientists around the world has shown that preliminary concentration processes lead to the use of various sorbents and organic reagents. Abdel Moamen [6] carried out tests for the separate immobilization of cobalt and cesium ions from aqueous solutions using nano-sized gamma aluminum oxide. The functional groups, phase composition, surface morphology, and sorption properties of the synthesized nano-sized aluminum oxide were comprehensively analyzed.

The specific ecological effects of cobalt and chromium have been previously associated with inflammation, degenerative conditions, and cancer [7]. Recently, high levels of Cr and Co ions and the corrosion products released by biomedical implants have been identified as serious health problems. Biological reactions related to the toxicity of these metal ions have been analyzed,

revealing the presence of corrosion products in various concentrations and the corrosion of metal ions and metal particles.

In the works of Cunningham et al. [8], the effects of Co and Cr metal ions on certain tissue areas and their potential health consequences were compared. Surgical implantation primarily leads to the effect of ions and corrosion products such as Co and Cr ions.

Cobalt and nickel ions are beneficial to the body in the required amounts, but their excess has been studied for its harmful effects on the organism. According to the list of banned substances by the World Anti-Doping Agency, they are included in the group of erythropoiesis-stimulating doping agents [9].

Banerjee's research [10] has shown that toxic levels of cobalt often lead to harmful physiological effects, including structural disruption in biological systems, decreased photosynthetic activity, chlorophyll synthesis disruption, and the induction of oxidative stress. The study emphasizes that the excess amount of Co can be alleviated by physicochemical methods, bioremediation, and phytoremediation to prevent its impact through food.

In our scientific research, we have chosen a new reagent, **1-nitrozo-2-naphthol-3,6-disulfonic acid disodium salt hydrate (Nitroza R salt)**, for the sorption-spectroscopic detection of Co⁺² ion. $\lambda_{Rmax} = 376 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{Co+2max} = 419 \text{ nm}$; 520 nm .

Research Objects and Methods.

The research objects include soil, natural, and wastewater samples around Akhangaron cement plant, as well as environmental objects contaminated with Co(II) ions and their compounds. Photometric and spectrophotometric analysis methods were used in the research.

As the environmental object, initial investigations were carried out on soil samples collected around Akhangaron cement plant, and the amount of Co(II) ions in them was analyzed using mass spectrometric analysis (ISP-MS). The results of the analysis are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The amount of Co(II) ions in the soil of various areas at different distances from Akhangaron cement plant (µg/g):

1 km Distance (16.08 µg/g)

3 km Distance (15.3 µg/g)

5 km Distance (12.1 µg/g)

10 km Distance (5.5 µg/g)

Reagents and Equipment.

Cobalt (II) salts were prepared as standard solutions as described in the literature [11].

Table 1.

Metal salt formula	Molar mass of the salt, g	Mass fraction of the metal in the salt, %	Mass fraction of the salt in the crystalhydrate, %	Weight for 1 liter solution
Co (Ar =58,9332)				
CoSO ₄ × 7H ₂ O	281,10	20,970	55,14	0,4770
CoCl ₂ × 6H ₂ O	237,93	24,770	39,72	0,4037

For preparing the Nitroza R reagent solution (C₁₀H₅NNa₂O₈S₂, 377.258 g/mol), 0.3853 g of the reagent was taken and placed into a 100 ml flask, followed by the addition of 96% ethyl alcohol. The flask was shaken until the reagent dissolved, and then distilled water was added up to the mark. The solution remains stable for 30 days [11].

For the fiber sorbent, polyacrylonitrile (PAN) was modified with polyethylene polyamine (PEPA) to obtain the fiber used in the study [12]. The fiber sorbent was weighed on an analytical balance with an accuracy of 0.0001 g in amounts of 0.2 g. The solid fiber sorbent was then soaked in a 0.1 M hydrochloric acid standard solution for one day, followed by washing with distilled water until it reached pH-7, and stored in Petri dishes [12].

The pH of the solutions was measured using the pH/mV/TEMP Meter P25 Eco Met pH meter (Korea). Absorption spectra were measured using the "EMC-30PC-UV-1800 Spectrophotometer" (China) and "UV-5100 UV-VIS Spectrophotometer" (Germany). The IR spectra of immobilized organic reagents and their complexes were recorded on a Bruker Invenio-X (Germany) instrument in the range of 8000–400 cm⁻¹.

Method for obtaining immobilized reagents:

Several fiber polymer sorbents were tested, and the static exchange capacity and dynamic exchange capacity (SAC, mg-equiv/g) of the selected fiber sorbent were measured. These sorbents were then used as solid fiber carriers in subsequent work. To determine the dynamic exchange capacity, a specific amount of pre-weighed sorbent was placed in a special column with a diameter of 10 mm. A 1.0 M HCl solution was passed through the column at a known rate, after which the fiber was washed with distilled water until pH-7 was reached. An aliquot portion (25 ml) was titrated with a 0.1 M alkali solution using methyl orange as an indicator [13-15].

Dependence of the optical density of the Co²⁺ ion complex with Nitroza R reagent on the pH of the medium:

Procedure: First, Co(II) ions in soil samples were transferred into an aqueous medium as described in the literature [10]. Further studies were conducted to determine the amounts of Co(II) ions in the water sample before and after sorption.

In 25 ml volumetric flasks, 2 ml of 0.1% Nitroza R reagent solution and 10 ml of buffer solutions with various pH values were added. Then, 1 ml of the sample solution containing Co(II) ions was added, and the flask was filled to the mark with distilled water.

The pH values of the prepared solutions were measured using a PHS-3E pH meter (China). The optical density of the complex was measured using the spectrophotometers "EMC-30PC-UV" and "UV-5100 VIS" (Germany) at the wavelength of $\lambda_{\max} = 419 \text{ nm}$ for Co^{2+} .

($l=1$; $C_{\text{Co}^{2+}}=60 \text{ mkg/ml}$; $\text{Co}^{2+}\lambda_{\max}=419 \text{ nm}$ $C_{\text{HR}}=0,1\%$ 2ml)

Table 2.

pH	2,36	2,55	3,01	4,05	5,023	6,128	6,5	7,23	8,4	9,1	10.0
A	0,221	0,224	0,278	0,450	0,564	0,871	1,09	0,950	0,936	0,86	0,83

Figure 3.

R+Me ⁺	pH	1	2	2,5	2,8	3	4	5	6	6,5	7
ΔA											
NRS+Co ²⁺	Amino-Sulfuric Acid	0,1908	0,1935	0,209	0,257	0,433	0,441	0,497	0,568	0,592	0,573
	Universal	0,167	0,280	0,330	0,338	0,440	0,514	0,502	0,507	0,5085	0,490
	Sodium citrate	-	-	-	-	0,404	0,506	0,545	0,579	0,621	0,587

Discussion of Results: Determining the Maximum Absorption Spectrum of the Reagent
Methodology: To determine the maximum absorption spectrum of Nitrozo R salt reagents, we used an EMC-30PC UV-1800 spectrophotometer, comparing the results against a reference solution. For this purpose, a 50 ml volumetric flask was used to prepare a 0.0001 M solution of the reagents.

The obtained absorption spectra are presented below.

The maximum wavelength for the Nitrozo R salt reagent was determined to be 368 nm (light yellow color).

Determination of the Maximum Wavelength for the Complex:

Two 25 ml flasks were prepared, each containing 1 ml (10 μg) of cobalt solution and 10 ml of an appropriate buffer solution with a pH of 6.5. Immobilized carriers with selected organic reagents were added to each flask. The solution was mixed, and its optical density was measured at various wavelengths using a spectrophotometer with a cuvette thickness of 1 cm.

Figure 2: Dependence of the Optical Density of Nitrozo R Salt Reagent on Wavelength

Figure 3:

The maximum absorption spectrum of the Nitrozo R salt reagent is $\lambda_{\max} = 368$ nm.

The maximum absorption spectrum of the complex formed by the Nitrozo R salt reagent with Co^{2+} ions is $\lambda_{\max} = 419$ nm.

Figure 4:

Reflection Spectrum of the Complex Formed by Co^{2+} Ions with Nitrozo R Salt Immobilized on PPA1 Fiber:

PPA1 fiber

Immobilized Nitrozo R salt
Co²⁺ complex

It should be noted that when the reaction between the Nitrozo R salt reagent and Co(II) ions is conducted in solution, the maximum wavelength of the resulting complex is 419 nm. However, when using immobilized Nitrozo R salt, the maximum wavelength of the resulting complex shifts to 520 nm.

The contrast between the reagent and the complex formed in solution is 60 nm, while the contrast for the complex formed with immobilized Nitrozo R salt is 152 nm. This demonstrates the significant advantages of the sorption-spectroscopic method over traditional spectrophotometry.

Preliminary concentration studies revealed that using immobilized Nitrozo R salt reagent allows for the recovery of 97-98% of Co(II) ions transferred from soil into water.

Conclusions:

Identifying toxic ions in environmental objects, drinking water, and wastewater and studying their impact on human health is of critical importance. Our research has developed a new sorption-spectroscopic method for detecting cobalt(II) ions in environmental samples using immobilized organic reagents. The immobilization and complex formation processes have been optimized.

This method is distinguished by its higher sensitivity and efficiency compared to other optical techniques. Preliminary concentration studies confirmed that using the immobilized Nitrozo R salt reagent allows for the extraction of 97-98% of Co(II) ions transferred from soil into water.

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